

ELIXIR-IT Single-Cell Omics Community

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ELIXIR Communities

Single-Cell Omics (SCO) community is the new-born ELIXIR community facing the new challenges of Omic Sciences at the single cell level.

3D-BioInfo

Helps to understand the 3D structure of macromolecules like proteins and DNA.

Food and Nutrition

Aims to help us understand the effect of food choices on human health.

Proteomics

Develops and maintains sustainable proteomics tools and data resources.

Single-Cell Omics

Identifies and addresses challenges in single-cell and spatial omics.

Galaxy

Fosters a Galaxy community in Europe, together with Galaxy resources and training.

Intrinsically Disordered Proteins

Develops standards, tools and resources to help identify and characterise IDPs.

Systems Biology

Aims to make systems biology modelling a central pillar of research in biology.

Toxicology

Supports the integration of standards, tools and resources to aid toxicology research projects.

Marine Metagenomics

Develops a sustainable metagenomics infrastructure to nurture research and innovation in the marine domain.

Metabolomics

Provides the resources, analysis tools and infrastructure to help metabolite identification.

Federated Human Data

Develops long-term strategies for managing and accessing sensitive human data.

Human Copy Number Variation

Aims to make it easier to detect, annotate and interpret human Copy Number Variations (hCNVs).

Microbial Biotechnology

Helps the development of tailor-made microbes and biological systems.

Plant Sciences

Develops an infrastructure to facilitate genotype-phenotype analysis for crop and tree species.

Rare Diseases

Supports the development of new therapies for rare diseases.

Short community history

- 2020
 - **Community proposal** by Patricia Palagi, Irene Papatheodorou, Jessica Lindvall and Eija Korpelainen. 17 Nodes involved. Approved by the ELIXIR Heads of Nodes.
- 2021
 - AHM workshop "FAIR Data Management for Single Cell Omics"
 - **Community workshop**
 - Workshop for scRNA-seq data analysis trainers (in collaboration with GOBLET)
- 2022
 - **White paper** "Community-driven ELIXIR activities in single-cell omics" submitted to F1000 by Paulo, Naveed and Eija
 - **Community approved** by the HoN
 - **Implementation study** proposal "SCONE: Single Cell Omics Network for ELIXIR", 19 Nodes

ELIXIR SCO Community

19 countries involved

Community leads

Raffaele Calogero
(Elixir Italia)

Naveed Ishaque
(Elixir Germany)

Eija Korpelainen
(Elixir Finland)

Community Coordinator

Katharina Hell
(Communities Coordinator,
Elixir Hub)

Why SCO Community?

SCO encompasses multiple technologies enabling the profiling of various omic modalities at the single-cell level for characterizing many biological phenomena and exploring cellular heterogeneity.

(a) Current count of articles using SCO technologies and cumulative number of cells sequenced and deposited in public databases. (b) Number of tools developed specifically to work with SCO.

Why SCO Community?

As the scale and modality of data sets grow, new computational methods are required. Also, data need to be stored and annotated in FAIR manner. An international effort is demanded.

ELIXIR SCO community focus:

- Single-Cell Omics
- Spatial Omics

Many challenges identified:

- Fast-developing field
- Tools, datasets, technologies
- Dataset curation, scalability, programming language

White paper and community website

F1000Research

OPINION ARTICLE

Community-driven ELIXIR activities in single-cell omics [version 1; peer review: awaiting peer review]

✉ Paulo Czarnewski ³,
Patricia M. Palagi ^{4,6},
Tony Burdett⁷, Barbara Szomolay⁸, Pavankumar Videm⁹, Hans-Rudolf Hotz ⁶,
Irene Papatheodorou ⁹, Wilfried Haerty¹¹,
Roland Krause ⁵, Brane Leskošek¹⁰, Luca Alessandri³,
Maddalena Arigoni³, Tadeja Rezen¹⁰, Alexander Botzki ¹³, Polonca Ferk¹⁰, Jessica Lindvall¹,
Katharina F Heil ¹⁶

ELIXIR official SCO website:

<https://elixir-europe.org/communities/single-cell-omics>

Github Repository:

<https://github.com/elixir-europe/sco-community>

ELIXIR-IT SCO community

Established in 2022

Community leads

Raffaele Calogero
(UNITO)

Ernesto Picardi
(UNIBA)

1st Workshop (Virtual – February 2023)

- The ELIXIR-IT node (Prof. Graziano Pesole)
- ELIXIR-IT activities (Prof. Emidio Capriotti)
- ELIXIR-IT SCO Community (Prof. Raffaele Calogero)
- Community activities:
 - SCO benchmarks (Prof. Raffaele Calogero)
 - RNA editing in single cells (Prof. Ernesto Picardi)
- Q & A

> 80 participants

ELIXIR-IT SCO community

ELIXIR-IT SCO Community is focusing on

- Development of benchmarks for SCO
- Epitranscriptomics at the single cell level
- Characterization of stem cells
- Training – SCO courses

scRNA-seq hands-on course

(Torino 26th-29th September 2023)

ELIXIR-IT SCO community

ELIXIR-IT SCO Community goals

- **Tools**
 - Collect available methods for registration in bio.tools
 - Create a Slack channel to exchange information about software benchmarks and datasets for benchmarking
 - Explore OpenEBench for benchmarking SCO data analysis methods
- **Compute**
 - Explore the computing needs of SCO data analysis
- **Interoperability**
 - Define requirements for an efficient single cell omics FAIR data and metadata standards
 - Promote and disseminate the use of standards
- **Data**
 - Facilitate the creation of a national Federated EGAs for human data
- **Training**
 - Provide training in data analysis and standards to complement ELIXIR Nodes activities.

ELIXIR-IT SCO community

ELIXIR-IT SCO Community next activities

- Invite ELIXIR-IT Institutions
- Run a survey about available technologies, equipment and data
- Collect all tools developed by the ELIXIR-IT node
- Organize New Training Courses (next one in Bari in 2024)

ELIXIR-IT SCO community

ELIXIR-IT SCO Community benefits

- Second and third generation sequencing platforms (Omics Platform)
- Consolidated (10x) and new technologies (spatial transcriptomics) are coming (Omics Platform)
- Additional computing nodes (cpu + gpu)
- Training Courses

CNR.BiOmics

BIG DATA FOR BETTER LIFE

NextGenIT

Consolidation of the Italian Infrastructure
for Omics Data and Bioinformatics

Thank you!

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Email list:

- single-cell-omics-community@elixir-europe.org
 - Use the “[Join the Community](#)” button to join

Slack Channel:

- ELIXIR workspace (elixir-europe.slack.com)
- Channel: #community_singlecellomics